

**PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING ACCOUNTING COTTON PRODUCTION
AND PROCESSING IN THE CONDITIONS OF
MARKET RELATIONS**

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Introduction. The proclamation of sovereignty, the strengthening of the economic independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the establishment of market relations require an increase in the efficiency of using the existing production capabilities of the national economy in general, agriculture in particular, and its leading industry - cotton growing - in particular. Therefore, the current situation in the agriculture of the republic requires the development of scientifically based methods for choosing directions for the development of production intensification processes, taking into account regional, zonal, soil, natural and climatic features and new economic relations.

In this regard, it is important to note that the political and economic transformations taking place in the country, the transition to a market economy, necessitate a revision of approaches in determining the directions of agricultural development. The expanding sovereignty of the republic makes this task more and more real and corresponds to the policy of economic development in general.

For many years, the directions of development of agriculture, the proportions between its individual branches were determined by the supply plans launched from the center, the achievement of "cotton independence, the fulfillment of" international duty", which resulted in the complete dependence of the republic on the cotton monoculture, one-sided economic development, depletion of the soil and a drop in yields. The dominance of the cotton monoculture hindered the development of

effective agricultural production. Little land and productive resources were allocated for the development of food industries.

In the context of a gradual transition to a market economy and the development of new relations with other sovereign states, completely new, first of all, economic criteria for the profitability of the production of a particular product will operate. This approach, when developing directions for the development of agricultural production in the future, dictates the need to proceed from the following main parameters::

- maximum return on each hectare of land;
- addressing issues aimed at better providing the population with food;
- providing employment for the rural population;
- reducing water scarcity and finding ways to maximize returns per unit of irrigation water.

Taking into account these basic approaches, it is also necessary to take into account the long-term experience of the rural population, its specialization in the production of certain agricultural products, as well as the possibilities of harvesting, storing, processing and selling grown products.

In recent years, these factors have become increasingly taken into account, in particular, a lot of economic work has been done to eliminate the disparity, improve the structure of agricultural development. The accepted forecasts become more realistic. In the republic, plans for the production of cotton in terms of raw materials have been reduced by almost 900 thousand tons. This made it possible to reduce the area under cotton, which made it possible to do away with the monoculture of cotton, to intensify many crop industries and, above all, grain production, and to significantly expand the household crops of rural residents of the republic.

Thus, the market economy opens up the most favorable opportunities for

rational specialization of agriculture, since in its conditions enterprises themselves determine the structure of their production, dispose of the products produced and their own income. In the market, the winner is the one who creates the highest quality products with the lowest production costs. This increases the competition between commodity producers for the effective use of available resources by concentrating on the production of the most profitable product in these natural and economic conditions. The creation of processing enterprises at the place of agricultural production should also contribute to the deepening of specialization. This reduces production and sales costs, as well as product losses, which are prohibitive in agriculture. In cotton growing, during the harvest period, these losses amount to an average of at least 20% annually.

However, cotton growing in Uzbekistan will continue to be the core of the national economic complex and play a leading role in the economy of the republic. Cotton is on a par with bread, coal, iron, and oil in terms of its importance for the country's industry and national economy. More than 200 types of various products and products are produced from it. Of particular value are the best quality cotton fabrics, the highest grades of thread and others. From one ton of raw cotton, 320-340 kg of fiber, 560— 580 kg of seeds are produced. From this amount of fiber, 3500 m² of fabric is produced, and from seeds - 112 kg of oil, 10 kg of soap, 270 kg of cake, 17 kg of husk and 8 kg of lint.

From cotton growing, rural producers of the republic receive up to 70-75 percent of the total revenue of the public economy. Now almost 60% of the able-bodied rural population is employed in cotton growing. Three-quarters of the main production assets are concentrated and function here.

Cotton growing in the republic is developing on the basis of intensification at an ever-increasing level. However, positive changes in the level of cotton production

and the increase in the efficiency of the industry in recent years, as confirmed by the results of the analysis, have not occurred. But, nevertheless, in recent years, the process of intensifying cotton production in the Republic has relatively stabilized with the regularization of the acreage under cotton crops.

It should be noted that the average yield of cotton in the Republic of Uzbekistan is significantly lower than the yield in foreign cotton-producing countries. For example, this indicator for medium-fiber varieties, which reach 85% of the cotton produced in the Republic of Uzbekistan, is 17.8 in Israel, 15.0 in Australia, 11.0 in Egypt, and 10.0 c/ha in Syria. more than we have.

The slow pace of development of cotton growing, as studies show, is determined by many objective and subjective reasons.

Until recently, Uzbek cotton fiber was one of the best in the world in terms of quality, but in recent years its quality has deteriorated, and therefore the export supply of Uzbek cotton has decreased.

In order to restore the high competitiveness of Uzbek fiber, it is necessary to improve its quality, replace the production of varieties with low-quality fiber with high-quality varieties.

The quality of the fiber inherent in the genotype of the variety can not be improved at the subsequent stages of cotton production, so the main task in cultivation is to preserve the natural properties of the fiber. Its solution largely depends on the culture of agriculture, improving the efficiency of land reclamation, the development of cotton and alfalfa crop rotations, the introduction of scientifically based farming systems taking into account zonal conditions, the rational use of water, land resources and fertilizers.

Important in preserving the natural properties of the fiber are the conditions of harvesting, storage of the crop and the mode of primary processing of raw cotton.

Creating optimal conditions for growing cotton allows you to significantly increase the yield of the crop, and consequently, the yield of marketable products.

To achieve these goals, it is necessary to intensify activities aimed at identifying research works. Genetic and selection research is constrained by insufficient development of the theoretical foundations of selection, poor knowledge of the source material for selection in the genetic aspect, models of intensive varieties, their requirements for environmental conditions, the unpreparedness of new varieties for transfer to the state variety testing, poor development of non-traditional methods of genetics-selection of cotton.

New methods in breeding, widely used in many foreign countries, in particular the introduction of individual genes in the hereditary material belonging to other genera and species, allows you to purposefully change the genetic apparatus of plants. So, in the United States, with the help of genetic engineering, cotton varieties that are resistant to various pests have been bred. Using growth regulators and other advanced techniques, scientists can address the stressful effects of the environment and improve fiber quality, uniformity, and yield. Research and development in the US cotton industry is aimed at increasing the yield of cotton and improving the quality of fiber.

In Israel, the main objectives of scientific research in the field of cotton production were aimed in the past at increasing yields and water efficiency, which are now complemented by such tasks as the development of new varieties of cotton with higher fiber quality, as well as fine-fiber cotton resistant to difusarium wilt, pest control using integrated systems, the use of non-traditional sources of irrigation (sewage and underground salt water), weed control.

There are great opportunities to increase the efficiency of cotton growing in the Republic by improving soil fertility, developing proper crop rotations, and

applying fertilizers. According to the experimental cotton-growing stations, 70% of the arable land has a low humus content. The terms of autumn-winter works, thinning, watering and other works are violated. Losses during harvesting reach 20%.

In some farms, along with a decrease in the rate of production of raw cotton, the indicators of economic efficiency of cotton farming have also significantly decreased, production costs and labor intensity of products have significantly increased, and the profitability of production has decreased.

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